

The mechanism of e⁺/e⁻ annihilation photon pair entanglement.

Dr. D.A. Sinclair

Cambridge

david@s-hull.org

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Abstract

Historic work on entanglement has assumed that additional space time cannot be created locally and that particles are somehow distinct from space time. This view is wrong. Space time is created in tandem with particles like electrons etc. An electron contains a pair of rotating magnetic dipoles mutually pushed forwards and backwards in time. Protons and neutrons contain larger time displacements associated with Heisenberg struts [5].

The fact that a point in space time may have only one magnetic potential at any one time points to the mechanism of entanglement for a photon pair created by electron-positron annihilation: it involves the spreading out of a region of space time.

In this region of space time each photon in the entangled pair contains magnetic potential from the past and from the future. This is hard to describe in language to the reader should look at figure ?? (imagine two photons cut in half along thier direction of travel and they have swapped their top halves). The time gap between the half photons remains as the photons separate in space time smearing out the *gobbets* of space time they came from.

The act of interfering (observing) with one entangled photon concurrently interferes with the other and causes the stretched space time region to collapse concurrently. This forces the other photon into a state (because half of it exists at the same time at the other photon).

In the local time frame no information is transmitted faster than the speed of light but the topology of space time is stretched.

Keywords: *the mechanism of entanglement.*

1 Introduction

Maxwell's equation is single valued in the magnetic potential $B(t)$ and $B(t)$ is a vector. A single vector at a single point in space and time cannot point in two directions at once.

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mathbf{J} + \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \quad (\text{Maxwell's equation})$$

This is at odds with the notion of superposition. Either Maxwell's equation is wrong or something else is going on in superposition. This paper offers the creation of a new local region of space time as a better description of reality and visualises what this means for an entangled photon pair created by an electron - positron annihilation event.

The model for electrons and positrons is from [5] and describes leptons as rotating magnetic dipole pairs with one pair pushed forwards in time and the other pushed backwards in time

relative to each other. This model describes how leptons are created and offers a view on how charge is quantised. The paper further describes how larger space time displacements can be locked in implying that the nucleus of an atom contains a region of stretched space time.

This paper takes the *negative time* results of [1] as proof that space time differs inside the nucleus of an atom, specifically it is stretched rather than compacted due to the presence of energy as one might naively assume. It takes *less time for a photon to cross a nucleus* than to travel a distance corresponding to its diameter. The only model of physics that accounts for this is the *Heisenberg strut* model given in [5] where Heisenberg struts are locked in stretchings of space time between magnetic dipoles held in Sinclair pairs.

We briefly reprise the basic easiest to visualise mechanism for creating a small amount of space time in section 2.

This paper argues that what is happening in an *entangled* pair of photons is not evidence of superposition but is simply that one half of the magnetic field in each photon is separated in time from the other half. The photon exists in its own little bit of space time and when you observe one photon you collapse the stretched goblet of space time.

Section 2 reprises the process for creating the Maxwell's cups that hold a small *goblet* of stretched time. Section 3 shows the form of a pair of entangled photons that result from the annihilation of an electron-positron pair.

Section ?? argues that other forms of entanglement likely involve linking discrete regions of space time where time displacement couples magnetic potentials together.

2 Creating and holding open space time.

Figure 2 illustrates a Maxwell Spin Cup. The spin cup comprises two *goblets* of space time one displaced forwards in time and one displaced backwards in time (a Sinclair Pair), separated by some radial distance, each contains a magnetic potential. The goblets of space time rotate around an axis in space. The force that holds the two regions of space together is termed a time like force and is a bit like Heisenberg's uncertainty principle.

This model naturally gives rise to 8 distinct spin cups for the two possible senses of the magnetic fields and two directions of rotation.

There are eight possible configurations for a simple Maxwell Spin Cup. The magnetic field vectors [4] can be arranged [N-SS-N], [S-NN-S], [S-NS-N] and [N-SN-S] and the direction of rotation can be either clockwise or anti-clockwise. The eight possible Maxwell Spin Cups are illustrated in figure 2.

We introduce a compact naming convention for spin cups and label them according to the outside pole of the past dipole, the outside pole of the future dipole and the sense of the spin. An electron would then be a [NNu] or a [SSd] spin cup and a positron would be a [NNd] or a [SSd] spin cup. Neutrinos can be [NSu], [SNu], [SNd] or [NSd].

The spin up-ness and spin down-ness are governed by the pairings of the magnetic field vectors, either [N-SS-N] or [S-NN-S]. It is obvious that there is the possibility for spin up and spin down electrons to attract each other through rotating quadruple alignment if they share a common spin axis. As one has spin 1/2 and the other spin -1/2 the combined pair will have spin 0. This predicted behaviour corresponds to the creation of Cooper pairs [2]. Neutrinos are made from leptons by changing the direction of one magnetic dipole. Which dipole is shifted forwards in time accounts for much of the unfathomable behaviour of neutrinos.

2.1 Creation of Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2.1 shows the electric and magnetic fields of a photon plotted along a time or space axis.

Figure 1: A Maxwell Spin Cup with its Sinclair Pair. Rotating magnetic potentials hold the electrical potential in the vicinity of the cup away from zero. The two regions occupied by the magnetic potentials are displaced from each other in time and space. The fuchsia region is forward in time (displaced forward in time from the current time plane) and the blue region is displaced backwards in time.

As a photon passes a General Relativistic [3] space-time gradient the wave form is distorted. The distortion will become unstable if the fields become multi-valued for a given portion of the photon.

The conditions for a photon shedding a pair of Maxwell Spin Cups is likely to be very specific. The time dilation across the photon will likely have to align portions of the magnetic field that are the same length. The phase of the photon at the alignment point must be such that there is some relation between the energy stored in the magnetic potential and in the electric potential (probably near equality).

3 What a pair of entangled photons looks like.

An entangled photon pair is one in which the regions of magnetic potential on one side of each exist at a different time to the potential on the other side. They bound their own region of space time.

Figure ?? shows such a pair of entangled photons. The fuchsia coloured magnetic potentials are forwards in time and blue magnetic potentials are in the past.

This is consistent with a pair of photons being created by the annihilation of an electron positron pair where there is a time shift between the dipoles that give rise to the EM waves.

The blue portions exist at the same time as each other and the fuchsia portions exist at the same time as each other.

The 8 simple Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2: The 8 simple Maxwell Spin Cups for electron-spin-up, electron-spin-down, positron-spin-up, positron-spin-down and a bunch of neutrinos.

4 Future Work

The new time shift physics replaces anything involving superposition of states and will create generations of work to properly characterise. The author believes this may offer a clue as to how quantum computers are able to work in zeros time.

5 Conclusions

It is argued here that 'entanglement' can be accounted for via a mechanism that creates new space time through pushing *gobbets* of space time apart in the time axis and does not require any form of quantisation or superposition of state or additional dimensions. This is the likely mechanism behind apparent superposition of states. It is this concurrent time linking of distinct locations that gives rise to the possibility of quantum computing. Information does not travel faster than the speed of light in the entangled system.

General Relativity is odd, General Relativity where you can create more space time in local regions and then stretch the regions is very odd. Maxwell and Einstein are always right, it is you that is misguided.

Action at a distance is possible if you are allowed to create new *gobbets* of space time through pushing one magnetic dipole from a pair of magnetic dipoles into the future and the other into the past.

Quantum theory is wrong and you can have spooky action at a distance!

6 Acknowledgements

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Figure 3: Illustrative photon magnetic (blue) and electric (red) field strength along a time/space axis (black).

References

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Figure 4: Illustrative effect of local time like drag on one side of a photon. Note the blue field line becoming non singular valued as it passes a location with large GR gradient.

Figure 5: Illustrative a pair of entangles photons. Only the magnetic potential is shown. Fuchsia indicates shifted forwards in time, blue backwards in time. The Heisenberg links between the photons are shown in green.